

Supplementary Information

Unveiling the shift from proton-coupled to hydride-coupled electron transfer and its origin

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Computational Details

The calculations were performed using the Gaussian 16 revision C.01 program^[40] for the (L)Cu^{III}-OH complex (L = *N,N'*-bis(2,6-diisopropylphenyl)-2,6-pyridinedicarboxamide) as reported by Tolman^[29] and for the one electron reduced variant of this complex. The B3LYP functional^[41] with Grimme's D3 dispersion correction^[42] and the def2-SVP basis set^[43] was used. The solvation effects were described with the conductor-like polarizable continuum model (CPCM)^[44] using $\epsilon = 7.4$ (tetrahydrofuran).

The Gibbs free energies for the optimized structures were calculated as the sum of potential electronic energies (E^{el}) calculated at the B3LYP-D3/def2-SVP level with CPCM and the thermal enthalpic and entropic contributions to the Gibbs free energy (at 298.15 K) obtained from frequency analysis performed at the same level of theory: $G = E^{el} + [E^{ZPE} + pV + RT \ln Q]$, where E^{el} and Q are the zero-point vibrational energy and the molecular partition function, respectively.

To calculate species respective for the half-reaction thermodynamic cycles and the barriers for the reaction the ground states of the reactants the electronic ground states were used: singlet for Cu^{III}-OH and doublet for Cu^{II}-OH. The Gibbs free energy barriers for the reactions were calculated as the difference between the Gibbs free energy of the transition state (TS) and the isolated reactants. A value of $1.9\Delta n \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ has been applied to correct the computed values to the 1 mol L^{-1} standard state (a value of $1.9 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ corresponds to the conversion of a 1 bar standard state in the gas phase to 1 mol L^{-1} concentration in solution at 298 K; Δn is the change in the number of moles). To obtain the TS structures for the self-exchange reactions between the Cu^{II}-OH or Cu^{III}-OH complex and its hydrogenated form (Cu^I-OH₂ or Cu^{II}-OH₂) the bulky 2,6-diisopropylphenyl groups were replaced by methyl groups. The TS structures

were approximated by constrained geometries that imposed symmetry between the two Cu complexes. Specifically, corresponding Cu–X distances (where X refers to the ligating N atoms or the O atom of the OH/OH₂ group) were constrained to be equal across the pair, without fixing their absolute values. Similarly, the distances between the transferring hydrogen atom and the donor and acceptor oxygen atoms were constrained to be equal, to obtain a symmetric hydrogen-sharing configuration.

The atoms-in-molecules (AIM) approach implemented in the AIMAll program^[25] was employed to assess the redistribution of electron density during the reaction in the investigated systems. The atomic charges were computed based on the electron densities calculated at the B3LYP-D3/def2-SVP level for the optimized structures of the transition states and reactant complexes. Densities were integrated using the Proaim method with a ‘very fine’ interatomic surface mesh and a basin outer angular quadrature of 14 400 grid points (using 15-point Gaussian quadrature GS15). The AIM properties of the atoms with a Lagrangian $L(A) > 0.001$ a.u. were recalculated with the Promega algorithm. The AIM charges and volumes (calculated for the isodensity surface of 0.002 a.u.) of the defined group of atoms, that is the transferred hydrogen atom, the H-atom donor and the acceptor – Cu^{III}–OH or Cu^{II}–OH complex, were used to characterize the reaction.

Intrinsic reaction coordinate (IRC) structures were derived from the corresponding TSs employing the same computational level as used for geometry optimization. To investigate the electron flow, we utilized IboView (iboexp=2)^[26,27] to generate and analyze intrinsic bond orbitals based on the wavefunctions obtained from the IRC points.

Table S1. Gibbs free energies of investigated species obtained at the B3LYP-D3def2-SVP level of theory. The values are given in Ha.

	G(subH)	G(catrad)	G(anion)	G(anionrad)	G(cation)	G(rad)
cyclohexane	-235.5870800	-235.3097579	-234.9897959	-235.5590716	-234.760616	-234.946117
cyclohexene	-234.3882162	-234.1454694	-233.8301481	-234.3908542	-233.5763406	-233.7625748
DHA	-540.2306420	-539.9973934	-539.712297	-540.2628994	-539.4399158	-539.614711
fluorene	-500.9662308	-500.7425842	-500.4633711	-501.0156151	-500.1438169	-500.3425738
Ph ₂ CH ₂	-502.1414053	-501.9012635	-501.6186285	-502.1728803	-501.3320865	-501.5153143
THF	-232.2104178	-231.9502539	-231.62241	-232.177506	-231.4114686	-231.5665919
toluene	-271.3042935	-271.0554534	-270.7553262	-271.3232365	-270.4655593	-270.6637219
2,7-di(NMe ₂) -fluorene	-768.6103731	-768.4387445	-768.0929585	-768.6392553	-767.7973427	-767.9841398
oxetane	-192.9099395	-192.6565777	-192.3316157	-192.8834777	-192.1085083	-192.264387
1,3-CHD	-233.1824648	-232.9655494	-232.6477766	-233.2228734	-232.3938172	-232.571178
CHD	-233.1691663	-232.9438527	-232.643756	-233.1813552	-232.3889642	-232.5578969
	G(Cu(II)-OH ₂)	G(Cu(III)-OH ₂)	G(Cu(II)-OH)	G(Cu(I)-OH ₂)	G(Cu(IV)-OH)	G(Cu(III)-OH)
CuIII-OH	-3233.659033	-3233.446508	-3233.186894	-3233.774325	-3232.795173	-3233.020498
	G(Cu(I)-OH ₂)	G(Cu(II)-OH ₂)	G(Cu(I)-OH)	G(Cu(0)-OH ₂)	G(Cu(III)-OH)	G(Cu(II)-OH)
CuII-OH	-3233.774325	-3233.659033	-3233.261305	-3233.825662	-3233.020498	-3233.186894

Table S2. Thermodynamic data for the investigated substrates and H-atom acceptors. The values were obtained at the B3LYP(D3)/def2-SVP level, with implicit CPCM solvation in THF at 298 K. All energies are given in kcal mol⁻¹.

substrates	ΔG_0 (half-reaction)	ω_{H^+}	μ_{H^+}	ω_{H^-}	μ_{H^-}
cyclohexane	-402.21	141.97	-180.73	-354.29	379.14
cyclohexene	-392.60	139.91	-199.88	-361.41	359.07
DHA	-386.50	126.50	-213.10	-365.17	336.55
fluorene	-391.35	123.89	-231.09	-386.83	343.01
Ph ₂ CH ₂	-392.88	125.41	-217.09	-373.07	345.14
THF	-404.01	145.47	-195.00	-339.90	369.11
toluene	-401.97	133.17	-214.46	-380.57	363.75
2,7-di(NMe ₂)fluorene	-392.97	153.43	-250.00	-373.57	347.95
oxetane	-405.09	144.19	-203.85	-343.87	367.35
1,3-CHD	-383.59	141.00	-208.98	-367.87	332.01
CHD	-383.58	133.16	-209.35	-351.60	340.78
H-atom acceptors					
CuIII-OH	-400.69	115.19	-262.86	-434.47	332.15
CuII-OH	-368.62	176.48	-242.51	-357.26	311.71

Table S3. Reactivity data for the **Cu(III)-OH**/substrate set (singlet). The values were obtained at the B3LYP(D3)/def2-SVP level, with implicit CPCM solvation in THF at 298 K. All energies are given in kcal mol⁻¹.

substrates	ΔG_0	ΔG^\ddagger	η_{H^+}	σ_{H^+}	$\Delta G_{offdiag}^{H^+}$	$\Delta G_{thermo}^{H^+}$	η_{H^-}	σ_{H^-}	$\Delta G_{offdiag}^{H^-}$	$\Delta G_{thermo}^{H^-}$
cyclohexane	1.52	15.30	-26.78	-82.13	13.84	14.60	80.18	46.99	-8.30	-7.54
cyclohexene	-8.09	9.72	-24.72	-62.98	9.57	5.52	73.05	26.92	-11.53	-15.58
DHA	-14.18	2.64	-11.31	-49.76	9.61	2.52	69.29	4.39	-16.23	-23.32
fluorene	-9.34	7.15	-8.70	-31.77	5.77	1.10	47.63	10.85	-9.20	-13.86
Ph ₂ CH ₂	-7.81	8.08	-10.21	-45.77	8.89	4.98	61.39	12.99	-12.10	-16.01
THF	3.32	12.31	-30.27	-67.86	9.40	11.06	94.56	36.96	-14.40	-12.74
toluene	1.28	16.24	-17.98	-48.40	7.60	8.24	53.90	31.60	-5.57	-4.94

Table S4. Reactivity data for the **Cu(II)-OH**/substrate set (doublet). The values were obtained at the B3LYP(D3)/def2-SVP level, with implicit CPCM solvation in THF at 298 K. All energies are given in kcal mol⁻¹.

substrates	ΔG_0	ΔG^\ddagger	η_{H+}	σ_{H+}	$\Delta G_{offdiag}^{H+}$	ΔG_{thermo}^{H+}	η_{H-}	σ_{H-}	$\Delta G_{offdiag}^{H-}$	ΔG_{thermo}^{H-}
cyclohexane	33.59	36.69	34.51	-61.78	6.82	23.61	2.98	67.44	16.12	32.91
cyclohexene	23.98	25.45	36.57	-42.63	1.52	13.51	-4.15	47.37	10.80	22.80
DHA	17.88	10.62*	49.98	-29.41	-5.14	3.80	-7.91	24.84	4.23	13.17
fluorene	22.73	7.42	52.59	-11.42	-10.29	1.07	-29.57	31.30	0.43	11.80
Ph ₂ CH ₂	24.26		51.07	-25.42	-6.41	5.72	-15.81	33.44	4.41	16.53
THF	35.39	34.88	31.01	-47.51	4.12	21.82	17.36	57.40	10.01	27.71
toluene	33.35		43.31	-28.05	-3.81	12.86	-23.30	52.05	7.19	23.86
2,7-di(NMe ₂)fluorene	24.35	9.95	23.05	7.49	-3.89	8.28	-16.31	36.23	4.98	17.16
oxetane	36.47	33.37	32.29	-38.66	1.59	19.83	13.40	55.64	10.56	28.80
1,3-CHD	14.97	18.63	35.48	-33.54	-0.49	7.00	-10.60	20.30	2.42	9.91
CHD	14.96	10.54	43.32	-33.16	-2.54	4.94	5.67	29.07	5.85	13.33

*an estimate based on unfinished TS optimisation

Table S5. Charges and volumes (at isodensity surface 0.002) of the H atom, H atom donor (substrate) and H atom acceptor for stationary points obtained for **Cu(III)-OH** reactions

TS						
	q			V		
substrates	H	substrate	H-atom acceptor	H	substrate	H-atom acceptor
cyclohexane	0.295	0.062	-0.360	19.4	761.0	3879.6
cyclohexene	0.288	0.075	-0.366	20.6	713.8	3890.3
DHA	0.303	-0.018	-0.326	20.0	1354.3	3894.8
fluorene	0.363	-0.086	-0.279	18.0	1236.1	3895.6
Ph ₂ CH ₂	0.322	0.010	-0.335	19.0	1307.1	3888.7
THF	0.279	0.110	-0.392	20.5	561.2	3890.1
toluene	0.343	0.024	-0.369	18.9	753.4	3891.5
RC						
	H	substrate	H-atom acceptor	H	substrate	H-atom acceptor
cyclohexane	-0.037	0.018	0.018	42.4	759.9	3887.1
cyclohexene	0.008	-0.020	0.010	38.8	717.0	3881.3
DHA	0.047	-0.056	0.008	35.2	1355.6	3889.7
fluorene	0.033	-0.016	-0.018	39.1	1231.4	3898.6
Ph ₂ CH ₂	0.037	-0.047	0.006	36.3	1318.3	3886.7
THF	0.039	-0.052	0.012	36.7	563.5	3867.7
toluene	0.014	-0.006	-0.009	40.4	756.0	3891.8

Table S6. Charges and volumes (at isodensity surface 0.002) of the H atom, H atom donor (substrate) and H atom acceptor for stationary points obtained for **Cu(II)-OH** reactions

TS						
	q			V		
substrates	H	substrate	H-atom acceptor	H	substrate	H-atom acceptor
cyclohexane	0.538	-0.132	-1.406	14.0	772.8	3922.1
cyclohexene	0.558	-0.336	-1.224	13.8	736.5	3929.7
DHA	0.553	-0.700	-0.855	14.1	1380.6	3912.2
fluorene	0.472	-0.640	-0.835	15.7	1261.2	3916.8
THF	0.536	-0.092	-1.446	14.2	571.9	3925.4
2,7-di(NMe ₂)fluorene	0.512	-0.668	-0.846	15.0	1955.4	3916.3
oxetane	0.556	-0.107	-1.449	13.9	451.7	3922.7
1,3-CHD	0.516	-0.543	-0.974	15.1	702.8	3938.0
CHD	0.557	-0.534	-1.025	14.2	703.3	3935.2
RC						
	H	substrate	H-atom acceptor	H	substrate	H-atom acceptor
cyclohexane	-0.008	-0.031	-0.964	36.0	760.3	3928.2
cyclohexene	0.042	-0.064	-0.979	34.7	717.3	3931.4
DHA	0.080	-0.110	-0.970	34.2	1357.4	3937.5
fluorene	0.118	-0.167	-0.973	30.5	1231.9	3928.4
THF	0.029	-0.053	-1.073	35.0	564.4	3936.1
2,7-di(NMe ₂)fluorene	0.085	-0.114	-0.975	32.6	1925.5	3931.3
oxetane	0.023	-0.051	-0.975	35.6	444.1	3913.5

1,3-CHD	0.051	-0.062	-0.990	35.4	672.2	3935.3
CHD	-0.032	0.025	-0.994	40.9	668.8	3937.1

Table S7. Charges and volumes of the H atom and the donor/acceptor in self-exchange reactions

substrates	q		V	
	H	donor/acceptor	H	donor/acceptor
cyclohexane	0.111	-0.055	25.0	752.8
cyclohexene	0.109	-0.054	25.5	707.3
DHA	0.123	-0.061	24.6	1342.1
fluorene	0.129	-0.065	24.1	1215.1
Ph ₂ CH ₂	0.118	-0.067	23.7	1296.4
THF	0.131	-0.066	25.4	559.5
toluene	0.124	-0.062	25.3	745.0
2,7-di(NMe ₂)fluorene	0.134	-0.067	24.3	1907.7
oxetane	0.143	-0.076	24.8	436.4
1,3-CHD	0.103	-0.051	24.1	662.7
CHD	0.118	-0.059	24.9	662.3
Cu(III)-OH / Cu(II)-OH	0.647	-0.385/-0.243	8.892	1462.1/1457.0
Cu(II)-OH / Cu(I)-OH	0.637	-1.320	9.157	1511.1

Table S8. Change of charge, Δq , and volume, ΔV , on H atom, substrate fragment and H-atom acceptor upon RC-to-TS transition during reactions with **Cu(III)-OH** and **Cu(II)-OH**.

	Δq			ΔV		
	H	substrate	H-atom acceptor	H	substrate	H-atom acceptor
Cu(III)-OH						
cyclohexane	0.332	0.044	-0.378	-23.0	1.1	-7.5
cyclohexene	0.279	0.095	-0.376	-18.2	-3.2	9.0
DHA	0.255	0.038	-0.334	-15.2	-1.3	5.1
fluorene	0.330	-0.070	-0.261	-21.1	4.7	-3.0
Ph2CH2	0.285	0.057	-0.341	-17.3	-11.1	2.0
THF	0.240	0.162	-0.403	-16.2	-2.3	22.4
toluene	0.329	0.030	-0.360	-21.6	-2.5	-0.3
Cu(II)-OH						
cyclohexane	0.546	-0.101	-0.442	-22.1	12.5	-6.1
cyclohexene	0.516	-0.272	-0.246	-20.9	19.1	-1.6
DHA	0.473	-0.590	0.115	-20.0	23.3	-25.4
fluorene	0.355	-0.473	0.138	-14.7	29.3	-11.6
THF	0.507	-0.039	-0.373	-20.8	7.5	-10.8
2,7-di(NMe ₂)fluorene	0.427	-0.554	0.130	-17.7	29.9	-14.9
oxetane	0.533	-0.057	-0.474	-21.7	7.6	9.2
1,3-CHD	0.465	-0.481	0.016	-20.3	30.7	2.8
CHD	0.589	-0.559	-0.031	-26.8	34.5	-1.9

Table S9. Change of charge, $\Delta\Delta q$, and volume, $\Delta\Delta V$, on H atom, calculated with reference to the average of charge and volume on H atom in two respective self-exchange reactions, for **Cu(III)-OH** and **Cu(II)-OH** systems.

Cu(III)-OH	$\Delta\Delta q @ H$	$\Delta\Delta V @ H$
cyclohexane	-0.084	2.5
cyclohexene	-0.091	3.4
DHA	-0.083	3.3
fluorene	-0.025	1.5
Ph ₂ CH ₂	-0.061	2.7
THF	-0.110	3.3
toluene	-0.043	1.8
Cu(II)-OH	$\Delta\Delta q @ H$	$\Delta\Delta V @ H$
cyclohexane	0.164	-3.1
cyclohexene	0.184	-3.5
DHA	0.173	-2.7
fluorene	0.089	-0.9
THF	0.151	-3.1
2,7-di(NMe ₂)fluorene	0.126	-1.8
oxetane	0.166	-3.1
1,3-CHD	0.146	-1.5
CHD	0.179	-2.8

Figure S1. Oxidants and substrates used in the study.

Figure S2. Three-component thermodynamics model applied to the Cu(III)–OH-based set of reactions, ΔG^\ddagger vs: linear free energy relationship LFER (left); LFER with the effect of asynchronicity (middle); LFER together with the complete off-diagonal term (right) using the descriptors derived based on the $[H^+/e^-]$ cycle (top, mismatched model featuring high off-diagonal contributions) and $[H^-/e^-]$ cycle (bottom, model featuring lower off-diagonal contributions). The quality of correlations is assessed by the squared Pearson's coefficient (R^2).

Figure S3. Three-component thermodynamics model applied to the Cu(II)-OH-based set of reactions, ΔG^\ddagger vs: linear free energy relationship LFER (left); LFER with the effect of asynchronicity (middle); LFER together with the complete off-diagonal term (right) using the descriptors derived based on the $[H^+/e^-]$ cycle (top, model featuring lower off-diagonal contributions) and $[H^-/e^-]$ cycle (bottom, mismatched model featuring high off-diagonal contributions). The quality of correlations is assessed by the squared Pearson's coefficient (R^2).

Figure S4. Volume and charge of the transferred H moiety at the TS relative to the volume and charge at RC. The points are colored and shaded from dark blue (favored $[H_{\leftrightarrow}/e_{\leftrightarrow}]$) to dark red (favored $[H_{\leftrightarrow}^+/e_{\leftrightarrow}]$) to reflect the difference in off-diagonal thermodynamic contributions to the barrier, which originates from the two different $[H_{\leftrightarrow}/e_{\leftrightarrow}]$ and $[H_{\leftrightarrow}^+/e_{\leftrightarrow}]$ cycles presented in **Figure 1** in the main text.

Figure S5. Correlations between η obtained from the nonoperative (left) and the operative thermodynamic cycle (right) and the change of charge on the transferred H atom at the TS calculated with respect to: the average of self-exchange reactions (top) or the RC (bottom). The points are colored to reflect the preference towards one of the thermodynamic cycles (as measured by the $\Delta G_{offdiag}^\ddagger$ originating from the $[H^-/e^-]$ and $[H^+/e^-]$ cycles) - in blue (favored $[H^-/e^-]$, Cu(III)–OH-set) and red (favored $[H^+/e^-]$, Cu(II)–OH-set).

(a)

(b)

Figure S6. The IBO changes of the C–H bond along the IRC for (a) Cu(III)-OH with cyclohexane and (b) Cu(II)-OH with cyclohexane.

(a)

(b)

(c)

Figure S7. The intrinsic reaction coordinates and the important IBOs of **Cu(III)–OH**-based set of reactions. (a) Cyclohexane (b) Cyclohexene (c) DHA and (d) Toluene. For Toluene and DHA the reciprocal transfer occur before TS.

α IBO of the C-H Bond

β IBO of the C-H Bond

α IBO of the O LP

β IBO of the O LP

β IBO of the C-C Pi

(a)

Figure S8. The intrinsic reaction coordinates and the important IBOs of Cu(II)-OH -based set of reactions. (a) 1,3-CHD and (b) THF. Exhibiting normal PCET behavior.

Structural features of the transition states and adiabaticity of the reaction. Comparison of geometries of the transition states for $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}\text{-OH}$ and $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-OH}$ systems reveals that, as it can be expected for $\text{Cu}^{\text{II}}\text{-OH}$, the strongly hindered, endoergic reactions feature late TSs, with an elongated C-H bond and a short O-H bond (nearly formed). From a mechanistic perspective, the geometry of the transition state is somewhat reflective of the asynchronicity of the reaction, as reactions more asynchronous towards H^+ transfer feature more elongated C-H bond and a shorter H-O distance.

On the other hand, in the $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}\text{-OH}$ set the H atom is located at the midpoint between the donor (C atom) and the acceptor (O of $\text{Cu}^{\text{III}}\text{-OH}$). This characteristic is in line with lower ΔG^\ddagger and $\Delta G^\ddagger_{\text{H}^+}$ values for the reactions but also indicates that H^-/e^- transfer features stronger interactions between the substrate and the H-atom acceptor.

Figure S9. The crucial C–H and H–O distances at the TS, the points are colored and shaded from grey to dark blue to reflect the asynchronicity of the $[H^-/e^-]$ reaction and from grey to red to reflect asynchronicity of the $[H^+/e^-]$ reaction.